

The effect of application of waste glass cullet as a filler in a cleaner production of magnesium oxychloride cement composites

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ABSTRACT

The focus of this paper is to examine the potential of recycled waste glass cullet as a standard replacement (partial or full) in magnesium oxychloride cement-based construction composites (MOC). The glass cullet originating from waste glass bead recycling was first analysed and divided into size fractions approximately corresponding to the size fractions of the standard filler. Then it was used in the amounts of 25, 50, and 100 wt% relative to the amount of the standard quartz sand filler, and its effect was assessed in comparison with a reference sample filled with the standard filler only. The MOC-based composite samples that were prepared underwent a comprehensive analysis focusing on their phase and chemical composition (X-ray analysis XRD resp. XRF and SEM/EDS), microstructure (SEM, OM), morphology, fundamental physical (determination of dry powder density, specific density, water absorption) and mechanical properties (flexural and compressive strength and dynamic Young's modulus), hygrothermal performance, and durability in relation to water exposure. As the recycled waste glass cullet contained Zn, Se, and Cd, special attention was paid to the testing of their potential leaching from the prepared composite materials. It was shown that the tested approach provides MOC-based composites with good material properties suitable for various applications, which proves the great potential of recycled waste glass cullet as a filler in the preparation of construction composites beneficial in carbon offset and increased environmental sustainability.

1. Introduction

The recycling rate for packaging glass in the EU has reached a record high of 75.6 % [1], which represents an increase by approximately 5 % over the last 5 years. However, the situation varies significantly within individual countries. Belgium, Luxembourg, and Slovenia are leaders in glass recycling with nearly 100 % of glass returned to the system. On the other hand, Greece and Hungary have the lowest recycling rates, with less than 38 % of glass recycled. Many glass manufacturing companies, like companies in the ceramic industry, aim to reduce their environmental impact by incorporating production waste back into their processes to reduce the effect on landfill capacity and, at the same time, reduce the consumption of natural resources. Decarbonisation, together with recycling and circular economy, is the key environmental

management of all fields of today's industry. Nevertheless, a significant amount of glass waste remains untapped. The reason may be the different approach of individual countries to the processing of large-volume cullet (plate and packaging glass), see above. The second reason in the case of small-volume waste placed in landfills is a certain specificity of the waste (screens, lamps, coloured beads, etc.), which is a certain obstacle to their subsequent use [2].

The manufacturing sectors are exploring novel approaches to reduce their carbon footprint and maximise the potential of waste materials that would otherwise go to landfills. The construction industry constitutes a fundamental pillar of social development, significantly influencing the built environment. The construction sector is a major contributor to global CO₂ emissions, and cement production accounts for a significant portion. According to the UN Environment Programme (UNEP) and the

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Fig. 1. Glass tubes before preparation by sieving: recycled waste glass cullet with colour scale, microphotographs from an optical microscope and electron microscope (left to right).

Global Alliance for Buildings and Construction, the sector accounts for approximately 38–40 % of global energy-related CO₂ emissions. Around 10–11 % of these emissions arise from the manufacturing and transportation of building materials such as steel, cement, and glass. Furthermore, the extraction of natural resources, particularly sand for the production of mortar and concrete, exacerbates environmental degradation [3–5]. In this study, two approaches for the mitigation of the impact of the production of construction composites are explored. The first is the utilisation of waste material as a partial or full replacement of standard fillers in construction composites. This approach offers a sustainable alternative, reduces dependence on natural resources, and facilitates decarbonisation [6]. The second approach is based on the utilisation of an eco-friendly matrix for construction composites in order to replace traditional cement-based materials. The selection of an appropriate alternative can cause a significant decrease in the overall carbon footprint of the resulting composite [7].

The use of waste materials as secondary fillers in construction composites is a widely researched topic. Today, many types of waste, such as ceramics, construction waste, waste wood, ash from incineration of various types of fuel, waste rubber, or waste glass, are studied as a potential replacement for standard fillers and aggregates [8–17]. The use of glass waste as a fine aggregate replacement was shown to be beneficial for pozzolanic activity and moderation of expansion of the prepared material after 28 days of curing [18]. Another study showed that the replacement of natural aggregate by glass aggregate in the amount of 5–20 wt% helps in terms of water absorption by capillarity and carbonation resistance [19]. It was also shown that waste glass powder can work as an eco-friendly admixture in high-performance white concrete for architectural applications [20].

Research on an eco-friendly alternative to ordinary Portland cement concerns multiple types of cementitious materials, such as calcium sulfoaluminate cement, alkali-activated cement, geopolymers, or reactive magnesia-based cements, such as magnesium potassium phosphate or magnesium oxychloride cement (MOC) [21–25]. MOC, especially in the form of phase 5 (5Mg(OH)₂•MgCl₂•8 H₂O), is a promising construction material due to its high early strength [26], fire resistance [27], and low thermal conductivity [28]. MOC is a sustainable and environmentally friendly type of cement material that has many advantages over traditional Portland cement [25]. However, its practical applications are limited by its poor water resistance. Previous studies have shown that the addition of specific functional additives, such as inorganic salts (sulphates, phosphates), carbon nanomaterials, or organic compounds, can improve water resistance [29–33]. The modified composites possess improved microstructure, lower porosity, and therefore a decreased proneness to water-induced damage [29,34–36].

This study presents experiments combining both of the above-mentioned approaches – designing a composite using MOC as an eco-friendly matrix and recycled waste glass cullet as either a partial or full replacement of the standard quartz sand filler. The tested recycled

waste glass cullet originates from the production of glass beads. The glass waste, in the form of tubes, is a semi-finished product from the manufacturing of Preciosa Rocailles glass beads. These round-shaped seed beads are produced using a unique technology that involves cutting glass tubes with round or square holes into pieces of various sizes. The pieces are then rounded and polished while hot, followed by classification based on size and shape. A portion of the red glass tubes must be excluded from production when the colour of the beads deviates from the desired standard. Currently, this waste has no secondary purpose and is consequently disposed of in landfills. Preciosa Rocailles are the most widely used type of glass seed beads. These beads have been industrially produced in Bohemia since the 18th century, though their origins trace back to Venice, Italy, in the 15th century. They are utilized globally in a variety of applications, including costume jewellery, hobby crafts, Christmas decorations, clothing and shoe embroidery, appliques, fashion and home accessories, as well as in traditional seed bead products such as ethnic souvenirs crafted by Indigenous peoples of the Americas, African tribes, and various Asian communities. Given that the waste red glass contains elements such as Zn (zinc), Se (selenium), and Cd (cadmium), it is essential to identify an application for this material. In a previous experiment, it was successfully tested as a melting component for the production of stoneware glass-ceramics [2]. In this experiment, the content of its size fractions in MOC-based composites was determined based on previous publications dealing with the processing of waste glass in Portland cement (PC) [5] and the testing of various fillers in MOC [37,38]. The proposed approach facilitates not only the reduction of quartz sand consumption but also, through the utilisation of a waste material that has not yet found its purpose, it could potentially help to reduce the burden on landfills. Finally, this approach offers a new type of eco-friendly composite material with good basic physical and mechanical properties, which provides a wide application potential. Furthermore, this glass cullet shows a promising route in the immobilisation of the potentially hazardous elements such as Zn, Cd, and Se.

2. Experimental

2.1. Characterisation of input raw materials

The used raw materials for the preparation of the proposed MOC-based composite samples were the following: raw materials for MOC production – magnesium oxide (MgO) and magnesium chloride hexahydrate (MgCl₂•6 H₂O); recycled waste glass cullet from glass bead manufacturing (termed C), and silica sand (termed PG).

2.1.1. Raw materials for MOC production

The raw materials for MOC production were MgO (98 % purity, Penta, s.r.o., Czech Republic) and MgCl₂•6 H₂O (p.a. purity, Lach-ner, s. r.o., Czech Republic).

Fig. 2. Microphotographs of three fractions of recycled waste glass cullet (C1, C2, C3): obtained from OM (left), SEM micrographs (middle), and particle size distribution curves obtained from LD for C1 and C2 and from IA for C3 (right).

Table 1

Chemical composition of glass waste - fractions C1, C2, C3 in wt% with highlighted selenium and cadmium oxides.

	B ₂ O ₃	F	Na ₂ O	MgO	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	SO ₃	Cl	K ₂ O	CaO	TiO ₂	Fe ₂ O ₃	ZnO	SeO ₂	ZrO ₂	MoO ₃	CdO	Nd ₂ O ₃
C1	1.60	0.84	18.70	1.20	0.64	62.33	0.31	0.04	5.37	2.35	0.03	0.04	5.95	0.11	0.01	0.04	0.45	-
C2	1.00	0.74	18.67	1.17	0.66	62.81	0.30	0.04	5.25	2.33	0.03	0.02	5.94	0.11	0.01	0.04	0.55	0.02
C3	1.30	0.80	18.77	1.17	0.66	62.44	0.30	0.03	5.41	2.37	0.02	0.03	5.93	0.12	0.01	0.04	0.58	-

2.1.2. Recycled waste glass cullet (C)

The red waste glass in the form of glass tubes (Preciosa Ornela a. s., Czech Republic) shown in Fig. 1 was milled in an industrial mill and subsequently divided into three size fractions through sieving: fraction C1 is in the size range of 0–0.25 mm; C2 in the size range of 0.25–1 mm and C3 in the size range of 1–2 mm. The specified size fractions were required by the glass waste manufacturer so that they could be used for testing other secondary applications (blasting ballotine, fillers for plastics, etc.). Sieving was carried out on standardized sieves for standardized sieve analysis. The glass tubes were crushed into cullet of very irregular shapes, including sharp-edged longitudinal ones presented in Fig. 2. Therefore, the size range of the fractions given by the sieve size

differs from the particle size curves obtained from laser diffraction (LD). The third coarsest fraction was evaluated using particle size analysis by image analysis (IA) and corresponds more to the size range given by sieving.

The chemical composition of all three fractions (C1, C2, C3) was identical, consisting of soda-potash glass with boron and calcium admixtures, and the colouring components were combinations of Zn-Cd-Se-S elements. The chemical compositions of the individual size fractions (XRF) are presented in Table 1. The primary colouring elements (Se and Cd) are highlighted in yellow within the table. The homogeneity of their distribution within the glass matrix is confirmed by energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) results shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. SEM micrographs of red cullet and EDS elemental maps of Cd and Se.

Fig. 4. Microphotographs of three sand fractions: PG1 0–0.5 mm, PG2 0.5–1 mm, PG3 1–2 mm.

Table 2
Mixture proportions of raw materials for the preparation of MOC-based composites.

Material/ Sample	Sorel cement (g)			Filler (g)					
	MgO	MgCl ₂ .6H ₂ O	H ₂ O	Silica sand			Glass recycle		
				PG1 0–0.5 mm	PG2 0.5–1 mm	PG3 1–2 mm	C1 0–0.25 mm	C2 0.25–1 mm	C3 1–2 mm
MOC-REF	709.9	716.2	444.2	709.9	709.9	709.9	-	-	-
MOC-C–25 %	709.9	716.2	444.2	532.4	532.4	532.4	177.5	177.5	177.5
MOC-C–50 %	709.9	716.2	444.2	355.0	355.0	355.0	355.0	355.0	355.0
MOC-C–100 %	709.9	716.2	444.2	-	-	-	709.9	709.9	709.9

Fig. 5. Filler fractions for the preparation of MOC-C samples: MOC-C-25 %, MOC-C-50 %, MOC-C-100 % (left to right).

Fig. 6. Comparison of filler fractions: mixture of PG fractions, C1, C2, and C3 (left to right).

Fig. 7. Particle size distribution curves for the quartz sand (PG) and glass waste (C) fractions.

Phase composition measurements (XRD) of all fractions of milled glass waste demonstrated the presence of compounds that form molecular dyes. For identification, ICDD cards 04-020-5584 (Cadmium Selenide Sulphide) and 04-003-9925 (Zinc Cadmium Selenide) were used. Fig. S1 shows the X-ray patterns of all three fractions (C1, C2, C3) with the identified phases with their main peak positions at $2\theta = 24.45^\circ$, 25.99° , and 27.76° . These components are used in this combination as an intense dye, with cadmium selenide sulphide being the primary source of the bright red colour.

Table 3
Physical properties of C and PG fractions.

Material	Powder density uncompactd	Powder density compactd	Specific density ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)	Thermal conductivity ($\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$)	Volumetric heat capacity $\times 10^{-6}$ ($\text{MJ}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$)	Thermal diffusivity $\times 10^{-6}$ ($\text{mm}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$)
C1	1182	1598	2575	0.3167	1.3507	0.2294
C2	1269	1540	2569	0.3023	1.2838	0.2354
C3	1168	1339	2564	0.2229	0.9029	0.2469
PG1	1354	1569	2663	0.2685	1.5168	0.1770
PG2	1432	1577	2638	0.2730	1.5134	0.1804
PG3	1462	1600	2662	0.2993	1.491	0.2007

2.1.3. Quartz sand

Quartz sand (Filtirační písky, spol. s r.o., Czech Republic) was used as a filler in three size classes: PG1 (0–0.5 mm), PG2 (0.5–1 mm) and PG3 (1–2 mm). The morphology of the individual fractions was studied using OM, see Fig. 4.

2.2. Composite sample preparation procedure

The compositions of the raw material mixture used for the preparation of the MOC-based composites are presented in Table 2. The mixtures always contained the same ratio of the raw materials for MOC and differed in the content of the recycled waste glass cullet (C) and quartz sand (PG) used as fillers. The ratio of raw materials for MOC preparation was chosen based on previous research [39]. It is a stoichiometric ratio of raw materials for the synthesis of the desired Phase 5. No retarder was used in the preparation of the MOC composites, as it was not necessary to control the workability of fresh mixtures. The samples were designated as follows: the reference mixture (MOC-REF) contained PG as a filler in three size fractions (PG1, PG2, PG3), while the other [39] mixtures, MOC-C-25 %, MOC-C-50 %, and MOC-C-100 %, the sand was gradually replaced with glass waste (C) of a similar size fraction in the amount of 25, 50 and 100 wt% in each size fraction, respectively. The filler mixtures used in MOC-C-25 %, MOC-C-50 %, and MOC-C-100 % are shown in Fig. 5, and the comparison between the individual C fractions and the PG mixture is shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 7 illustrates the comparison of grain size distribution curves for crushed cullet C1–C3 and PG1–PG3 blends, obtained by standard sieve analysis. Notable differences between the two fillers were detected solely within the 0.2–1.0 mm range. Outside of this range, the grain size curves exhibited considerable similarity.

Table 3 provides the physical parameters of the glass recycle and silica sand fractions. Thermal properties are specified for fully compacted samples, while powder density was investigated for both uncompactd and compactd fillers. The water absorption for cullet C

Fig. 8. A scheme of recycled waste glass cullet production and application in MOC-based composites.

was determined to be zero, whereas values of 0.233 wt%, 0.256 wt%, and 0.266 wt% were recorded for PG1, PG2, and PG3, respectively.

In the initial step, $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was fully dissolved in tap water. Subsequently, MgO was introduced to the solution. The suspension was mixed in a planetary mortar mixer at low speed (140 rpm) for 30 s. Then the filler (either PG, C, or their mixture) was added. The mixing continued for another 30 seconds at a low speed and then for 4 minutes at a high speed (285 rpm). The prepared mixtures were poured into moulds with dimensions of $40 \times 40 \times 160$ mm (Fig. 8). The prismatic samples were demoulded after 24 hours and left to cure in a climatic chamber at $T = 23 \pm 2$ °C, $RH = 50 \pm 5$ % for another 27 days. The selected curing conditions were deemed appropriate for facilitating the development of phase 5.

2.3. Methods and instruments

Detailed analyses and their evaluation were conducted on perfectly matured samples after 28 days of curing in moulds.

The particle size distribution was analysed by the laser diffraction

(LD) method using a Malvern Panalytical Mastersizer 3000 device with a 4 mW He-Ne 632.8 nm red light source and a 10 mW LED 470 nm blue light source. The measurement range was set from 0.01 to 3000 μm . Prior to each measurement, the system automatically calibrates the positions of all detectors based on the intensity of the detected red and blue light, ensuring high measurement accuracy. The measurement was carried out in a wet cell using isopropyl alcohol (Penta, purity p.a.). During the measurement, a constant mixing of the suspension was set (3000 rpm). The sample was measured 5 times (5 scans), and the distribution was created from the average value. For precise particle size calculations, the sample's refractive index was specified. This study employed Mie theory for particle size analysis, enhancing precision, especially for non-spherical particles. This method was used for the size fractions C1 and C2. Due to the larger size of fraction C3 and the limitations of this device, the particle size distribution of this fraction was determined using image analysis (IA). Macro-optics Navitar, combined with a Sony 2/3 camera with a resolution of 5 MPix, was used to obtain detailed pictures. The NIS-Elements BR 5.21.02 software with an Extended Depth of Focus Module (EDF) was used for imaging and

Table 4
Basic structural properties of MOC-C and MOC-REF.

	Matrix density ρ_{mat} ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)	Bulk density ρ_b ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)	Total open porosity ϕ (%)	Open pore volume V_{op} ($\text{cm}^{-3}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$)	Average pore diameter d_n ($\text{cm}^{-3}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$)
MOC-C–100 %	2253 ± 27	2002 ± 28	11.2 ± 0.2	0.0661	0.0387
MOC-C–50 %	2269 ± 27	2030 ± 28	10.5 ± 0.2	0.0573	0.0420
MOC-C–25 %	2266 ± 27	2033 ± 28	10.3 ± 0.2	0.0572	0.0464
MOC-REF	2279 ± 27	2039 ± 29	10.7 ± 0.2	0.0649	0.0466

analysis of the samples. ImageJ free evaluation software was used for image analysis. The particle size calculation software was calibrated using a scale that was part of the image observed from Macro optics. The C3 particles were measured multiple times, and the resulting distribution was calculated from the obtained values.

Furthermore, the grain size curves corresponding to silica sand mixed from the PG1-PG3 fractions and those of glass granulated mixed from the C1-C3 fractions were measured by standard sieve analysis.

The determination of the chemical composition was performed using an X-ray fluorescence (XRF) Axios PANalytical sequential spectrometer. The acquired data were evaluated by Omnian standard-less software and calculated as oxides normalised to 100 %.

The mineralogical compositions were identified by X-ray diffraction (XRD) using a PANalytical X'Pert³ Powder diffractometer. CuK α radiation was used in the angular range of 5–80°. Semi-quantitative and quantitative analysis was performed using Panalytical High Score Plus software and RIR (Reference Intensity Ratio) values from the PDF5 + database. Quantitative phase analysis and consideration of the presence of a non-crystalline phase were carried out by the internal standard method with the addition of 10 wt% of ZnO in the measured powder sample.

The evaluation of the fundamental **physical properties** of both fillers involves the determination of dry powder density, specific density, water absorption, and thermal parameters such as thermal conductivity, thermal diffusivity, and volumetric heat capacity. Measurements were conducted on both uncompact and fully compact samples. The specific density was assessed using the helium pycnometry principle. The ISOMET 2114 non-stationary heat pulse technique work device ISOMET 2114 (Applied Precision) was utilised for measuring heat transport and storage. Further details on the applied measurement methods can be found, e.g., in [40,41].

The microstructure and morphology of the input raw material of

waste glass fractions and the prepared MOC-based composites were evaluated using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) through the Tescan Lyra 3 apparatus. The microscopic analysis was supplemented with the measurements of chemical composition by an energy dispersive spectrometer (EDS).

Microscopic observations were performed by optical polarisation microscopy (OM) using the Olympus BX51 polarising optical microscope with the Canon 500D digital SLR camera and the Olympus SZ61 stereomicroscope with the ProgRes CT3 digital camera. The images were processed in NIS Elements AR 4.60 and ZoomBrowser EX software.

Colour measurements of MOC-based composite samples with varying amounts of coloured waste glass fractions were carried out using a vertically aligned portable spectrophotometer, Konica Minolta C-700dm, in the wavelength range of 400–700 nm with 8° sphere geometry and simultaneous SCI and SCE measurement.

The **macrostructural parameters** of the composites investigated include dry bulk density, specific density, and total open porosity. The dry bulk density was assessed using the gravimetric procedure prescribed in EN 1015–10 [42]. Matrix density was measured using a helium pycnometer, Pycnomatic ATC (Thermo Fischer Scientific). The total open porosity calculations were based on bulk density and specific density data [40]. **Microstructural parameters** of the composites were examined through mercury intrusion porosimetry (MIP), utilizing a series of porosimeters from the Pascal series (Pascal 140 + 440, Thermo Fischer Scientific). The parameters analyzed included total pore volume and average pore volume, determined from incremental and cumulative pore size distribution curves. **Mechanical properties** such as flexural and compressive strength and dynamic Young's modulus were evaluated. These strength tests conformed to EN 1015–11 [43], with the flexural strength assessment employing a three-point bending test configuration. The dynamic Young's modulus was determined using an ultrasonic apparatus, Vikasonic (Schleibinger Geräte). The **thermal**

Fig. 9. Pore size distribution: a) incremental curves, b) cumulative curves.

Table 5
Mechanical properties of MOC-based samples with C after 28 days.

	Flexural strength f_f (MPa)	Compressive strength f_c (MPa)	Young's modulus E_d (GPa)
MOC-C-100 %	12.01 ± 0.17	60.24 ± 0.84	32.24 ± 0.45
MOC-C-50 %	12.04 ± 0.17	67.40 ± 0.94	33.91 ± 0.48
MOC-C-25 %	15.04 ± 0.21	79.51 ± 1.11	36.36 ± 0.51
MOC-REF	12.95 ± 0.18	71.45 ± 1.00	34.72 ± 0.49

conductivity, thermal diffusivity, and heat storage capability were examined with a thermophysical tester, HotDisk TPS 1500, equipped with a Kapton-insulated sensor. **Water resistance** was quantified by the softening coefficient, defined as the ratio of the compressive strength of a sample submerged in water for 24 hours to that of a control sample stored in laboratory conditions. Given that water resistance is impacted by excessive moisture ingress, the 24-hour water absorption and water absorption coefficient were analysed in accordance with EN 13755 [44] and EN 1015-18 [45].

The **immobilization ability** of the prepared composites towards cadmium, selenium, and zinc was measured by inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) on leachates from the immersion of the composite samples in water using the Agilent 5900 instrument equipped with a synchronous vertical dual view. Leachates were prepared according to standard EN 12457-2 [46] with a liquid to solid ratio of 10:1. In contrast to the standard, the samples were only immersed in water and not stirred. The quantitative analysis was allowed by the use of a 5-point calibration curve for each element measured. Each sample was measured in 3 duplicates with 5 s reading time each. Spectral intensities for Cd, Se, and Zn were measured at the wavelengths of 214 nm and 196 nm, respectively. The measured data were evaluated by the ICP Expert Pro Software.

3. Results and discussion

The prepared MOC-based composite samples showed in **Figure S 2** were subjected to a series of analyses after 28 days of curing.

The values of the macrostructural and microstructural parameters presented in **Table 4** are in accordance with the change in composition of samples. The data obtained for matrix density, bulk density, and total open porosity are given, including their expanded combined uncertainties. With an increasing content of glass recycle, the bulk density decreased, as glass has a lower density than sand. The matrix density values primarily fluctuated within the bounds of measurement uncertainty, exhibiting a slight tendency to decrease. This tendency may be attributed to the porosity of coarser glass recycle particles of fraction C3, as apparent from **Fig. 2**. The total open porosity did not change significantly because the sand fractions were replaced by glass fractions of similar sizes. The cumulative and incremental pore size distribution curves used for the calculation of microstructural characteristics of composites are shown in **Fig. 9**. The data of open pore volume V_{op} followed the trend of open porosity. The average pore size was apparently decreased by the silica sand substitution with glass recycle, which evinces effective packing of glass particles in the MOC matrix. This phenomenon may also be attributed to the increased fineness of the glass cullet within the particle size range of 0.2 mm to 1.0 mm.

The mechanical parameters measured for 28-day samples are summarised in **Table 5**. The mechanical properties of the samples with the waste glass cullet were not significantly different from those of the reference sample. The MOC-C-25 % sample showed an increase in all measured mechanical properties, which correlates with the open porosity data and total open pore volume. Specifically, the flexural strength, compressive strength, and Young's modulus were enhanced by 16.1 %, 11.3 %, and 4.7 %, respectively. The findings imply that substituting 25 % of silica sand with waste glass favourably influences

Table 6
Thermal properties of MOC-based samples with C after 28 days.

	Thermal conductivity λ ($W \cdot m^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$)	Thermal diffusivity a ($mm^2 \cdot s^{-1}$)	Volumetric heat capacity c_v ($MJ \cdot m^{-3} \cdot K^{-1}$)
MOC-C-100 %	0.968 ± 0.021	0.430 ± 0.009	2.246 ± 0.051
MOC-C-50 %	1.603 ± 0.035	0.754 ± 0.017	2.130 ± 0.047
MOC-C-25 %	1.869 ± 0.041	0.943 ± 0.021	1.984 ± 0.044
MOC-REF	2.963 ± 0.065	1.295 ± 0.028	2.298 ± 0.051

the mechanical properties. In terms of mechanical resistance, a 25 % replacement of silica sand with glass recycle emerges as the optimal approach for producing high-strength composites. Nevertheless, from a sustainability perspective, a 50 % replacement of sand with recycled glass seems optimal, as the composite MOC-C-50 % demonstrated only a 7 % reduction in flexural strength, a 5.7 % decrease in compressive strength, and a 2.3 % decline in the dynamic Young's modulus. A complete replacement of sand with glass resulted in the lowest mechanical strength and stiffness, but the decrease in the recorded values of mechanical parameters was relatively small, with approximately 7.3 % for flexural strength, 7.1 % for elastic modulus, and 15.7 % for compressive strength when compared to the reference sample. In quantitative terms, the mechanical parameters of all analysed composites are substantial, facilitating wide applicability in the construction industry. The compressive strength of the prepared composites is comparable to that of high-strength concrete [47].

Table 6 presents a comprehensive summary of the thermal parameters of the composites. Despite the higher thermal conductivity and thermal diffusivity exhibited by the glass recycle fractions C1 and C2, in comparison to silica sand, the overall heat transport capacity of the composites was reduced due to the use of cullet. This phenomenon can be attributed to the worse compacting of glass recycle itself, as evidenced by the powder density data, and primarily due to the low thermal conductivity of fraction C3, which was the lowest among the fillers studied. The worse packing efficiency of glass recycle relative to that of silica sand can lead to the disparity in the interfacial characteristics between the glass recycle and the MOC matrix, which is constituted by needle-shaped crystals of phase 5. This variation results in the diminished heat transport within the MOC-C composites when compared to the reference material, MOC-REF. Given that silica sand demonstrates a greater volumetric heat capacity than ground cullet, the heat storage capacity of the composites was consequently diminished. Additionally, changes in the porosity of the composites, which are also affected by the nature of the glass recycle/MOC matrix interface, contributed to the variations observed in the heat transport and storage parameters.

The hygric properties shown in **Table 7** were evidently influenced by the minimal water absorption of the glass recycle itself. The hygric parameters assessed for the MOC-C composite were significantly lower in comparison to the reference material, MOC-REF. Nevertheless, the variations in porosity also impacted the observed moisture ingress, elucidating the increase in A_w and W_{a1D24} for MOC-C-50 % and MOC-C-100 %, relative to MOC-C-25 %. In the case of MOC-C-100 %, the increased porosity resulted in a W_{a24} value exceeding that obtained for MOC-REF. Despite the total open porosity, pore size affects the moisture transport in porous materials. Capillary pores, with diameters ranging from 0.005 μm to 10 μm , are generally considered responsible for water movement. In this respect, MOC-REF was observed to possess the maximum of capillary pores among the composites tested, which well correlates with its highest A_w and w_{a1D24} . Conversely, gel pores, characterized by a pore diameter of less than 0.005 μm , do not facilitate liquid water transport due to the strong adsorption of water molecules on their surfaces. The gel pore volume observed in MOC-C-50 % and MOC-C-100 % was evidently greater than that documented for the

Table 7

Hygric properties of MOC-based samples with C after 28 days.

	Water absorptiotablen coefficient A_w $\times 10^{-3}$ ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{s}^{-1/2}$)	1D 24 h water absorption W_{a1D24} ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$)	24 h water absorption W_{a24} ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)	Softening coefficient α_s (%)
MOC-C-100 %	3.6 ± 0.021	0.858 ± 0.009	71.6 ± 1.002	82.3 ± 1.6
MOC-C-50 %	3.3 ± 0.035	0.891 ± 0.017	66.6 ± 0.932	80.5 ± 1.6
MOC-C-25 %	2.9 ± 0.041	0.797 ± 0.021	66.4 ± 0.930	81.6 ± 1.6
MOC-REF	6.2 ± 0.065	1.117 ± 0.028	69.6 ± 0.974	89.4 ± 1.8

Fig. 10. Fracture surface micrographs of MOC-based composites: MOC-C-100 %, MOC-C-50 %, MOC-C-25 %, and MOC-REF.

reference composite, which aligns with their diminished capacity to facilitate water transfer. Overall, from a quantitative perspective, the A_w values acquired were significantly lower compared to materials that are highly absorptive and effective in transporting water [48,49], which aligns with the limited porosity of the composites and the efficient packing of their constituents.

Minimal alterations in the softening coefficient relative to the reference were observed for MOC-C-25 % and MOC-C-50 %. Although the integration of glass recycle partially hindered water absorption, the subsequent moisture uptake resulted in a strength reduction. This can be attributed to the progressive decomposition of the 5-phase in the presence of water into $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ and other water-soluble ions, as well as the hydration of residual MgO [50,51]. The formation of $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$, possessing a significant molar volume, consequently compromised the structural integrity of the composites, leading to a decline in mechanical

resistance. Nonetheless, the residual strength, recorded as 58.78 MPa, 64.02 MPa, 54.99 MPa, and 53.87 MPa for MOC-REF, MOC-C-25 %, MOC-C-50 %, and MOC-C-100 %, respectively, remained sufficiently high for structural applications. In the case of MOC-C-100 %, the softening coefficient showed improvement compared to the reference. This enhancement is attributable to slightly increased porosity, allowing the material to endure the crystallization pressures of $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ and demonstrating an overall reduced capability to absorb water. However, this material exhibited the lowest residual strength.

Fracture surfaces of the samples were observed using a stereomicroscope. Fig. 10 documents an increasing proportion of red glass waste at the expense of grey sand grains. The morphology of fracture surfaces of the prepared MOC-based composites was observed using SEM, see Fig. 11. The elongated rod-shaped crystals, which are typical for phase 5 in MOC systems, were present in all types of composite samples with C.

Fig. 11. SEM micrographs of MOC-based composite samples.

Table 8

Chemical composition of samples of MOC with C in wt%.

	MgO	CaO	SiO ₂	Cl	Al ₂ O ₃	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	Fe ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	ZnO	CdO	WO ₃	Cr ₂ O ₃	SO ₃	ZrO ₂	SeO ₂	MoO ₃
MOC-C-100 %	41.97	2.00	28.98	11.99	0.18	5.00	4.00	0.13	0.02	5.00	0.40	0.02	0.02	0.14	0.01	0.10	0.04
MOC-C-50 %	38.80	0.99	39.80	11.94	0.20	2.89	2.29	0.20	0.01	2.49	0.20	0.02	0.03	0.08	0.01	0.05	0.02
MOC-C-25 %	33.92	0.50	49.88	10.97	0.18	1.60	1.20	0.30	0.01	1.20	0.11	0.01	0.04	0.05	0.01	-	-
MOC-REF	37.11	0.06	49.14	13.04	0.20	-	0.06	0.3	0.01	0.02	-	0.01	0.04	0.03	-	-	-

Table 9

Colorimetric data of MOC-C composite samples measured on pressed powders and cut surfaces.

	Measured surface	Specular component	Colour values			8° gloss
			L* (D65)	a* (D65)	b* (D65)	
MOC-C-100 %		SCI	73.21	5.76	3.06	5
		SCE	73.06	5.75	3.08	5
		SCI	67.92	13.33	4.62	1
		SCE	67.88	13.26	4.63	1
MOC-C-50 %		SCI	75.44	3.45	2.66	6
		SCE	75.27	3.44	2.70	6
		SCI	75.76	6.79	2.51	1
		SCE	75.74	6.75	2.54	1
MOC-C-25 %		SCI	77.06	1.49	1.50	5
		SCE	76.91	1.49	1.54	5
		SCI	80.64	4.87	2.28	1
		SCE	80.61	4.84	2.33	1
MOC-REF		SCI	79.29	-0.17	0.16	5
		SCE	79.17	-0.16	0.19	5
		SCI	87.98	0.51	2.11	2
		SCE	87.94	0.51	2.16	2

Fig. 12. XRD patterns of the prepared MOC-based composites: MOC-C-100 %, MOC-C-50 %, MOC-C-25 %, and MOC-REF.

Particles of C are well distinguishable on micrographs, especially at lower magnification. Only a few macroscopic defects were detected for all samples at low magnifications. At higher magnifications, it is well visible that the glass phase is well incorporated into the MOC matrix, because the needles grow around the filler. The presence of these particles was also well manifested in EDS maps, which are shown further in the manuscript.

The homogeneity of the prepared samples was evaluated by mapping elemental distribution on fracture surfaces using EDS/SEM, see Fig. S3. The chemical composition in the bulk of the samples, determined on powders prepared by grinding the compact samples, is presented in Table 8. The data were further supported by SEM-EDS, which provided the elemental maps of the following elements: Si, Mg, O, Cl, and Na. The elemental maps are shown in Fig. S3.

The colour of the powders prepared by milling the MOC-based composites was determined on the tablets prepared for measurement of the chemical composition by XRF and cut surfaces of compact samples, see Table 9. Evaluation of colour measurement results with and without the specular component for individual measurements and sample types shows that inclusion of the specular component does not affect the change in colour of the measured material. This comparison is also supported by the measurement results of 8° gloss values, which express the surface gloss. The higher surface roughness of the cut surfaces leads to lower values of the gloss component compared to the measurement of powder samples. More interesting are the results of comparing the measured Lab coordinates of the CIELAB colour space for differently prepared samples, i.e., pressed powders and cut surfaces. In all cases, the colour difference is large and clearly visible. It has been demonstrated that colour can be assessed on both types of samples, depending on which is available, but always of the same type.

Table 10

The phase composition of the MOC-C and MOC-REF samples in wt%.

	Amorphous phase	SiO ₂ Quartz	Mg ₃ Cl(OH) ₅ (H ₂ O) ₄ Phase 5	(Mg ₂ (CO ₃)(H ₂ O)(OH)Cl).H ₂ O Chlorartinite	NaCl Halite	Zn _{0.3} Cd _{0.7} Se
MOC-C-100 %	62	1	34	2	1	traces
MOC-C-50 %	36	30	32	1	1	traces
MOC-C-25 %	18	49	32	1	traces	0
MOC-REF	6	61	31	2	0	0

Table 11

Leachability of prepared MOC-based composites with C during and after curing process.

	ICP					
	Cd (μg·L ⁻¹)		Se (μg·L ⁻¹)		Zn (μg·L ⁻¹)	
	24 h	7 d	24 h	7 d	24 h	7 d
MOC-C-100 %	1.31	0.66	1.74	<DL	10.01	2.88
MOC-C-50 %	0.39	0.28	<DL	<DL	9.78	2.44
MOC-C-25 %	0.20	0.28	<DL	<DL	2.55	2.07
MOC-REF	<DL	0.07	<DL	2.08	4.99	0.76

The phase composition of the samples was determined using XRD, the diffraction patterns of all samples, and the individual positions of the main peaks are presented in Fig. 12. For MOC and the products of its carbonation (chlorartinite), the main positions are $2\theta = 7.63^\circ$ (chlorartinite) and $2\theta = 11.89^\circ$ (MOC phase 5). The crystalline phase chlorartinite was identified in a small amount in all samples. This thermodynamically stable phase is formed during hydration and carbonation of reactive MgO-based cements as one of the hydrated magnesium carbonates according to the following equation [52]:

The formation of chlorartinite as a primary carbonation product under ambient conditions leads to a higher durability of MOC due to the prevention of water access and other degradation factors of MOC through a surface passivation [52,53].

Individual diffraction patterns with reference patterns of each

crystalline phase can be seen in Fig. S4. The comparison of the patterns of MOC-REF, MOC-C-25 %, MOC-C-50 %, and MOC-C-100 % manifests the decrease in the content of the quartz phase from 61 to 1 wt% as the filler is gradually replaced by C. Replacement of the filler is also demonstrated by the continuous increase of the amorphous phase (from 6 to 63 wt%), and detection of the colouring component $Zn_{0.3}Cd_{0.7}Se$ (traces) in the MOC-C-50 % and MOC-C-100 % samples. Traces or max 1 wt% of halite were identified in samples containing C. The quantification of the phase composition of the samples is summarised in Table 10.

The leachability of Cd, Zn, and Se was assessed via ICP-OES measurements for samples demoulded after 24 h and samples exposed to 95 % relative humidity in a climate chamber for periods of 7 days, see Table 11. Concentrations of Cd and Se in the leachate were negligible or below the detection limits, indicating minimal release of these elements. However, the leaching of Zn mainly immediately after casting was elevated and increased from 25 % addition to 100 % replacement of sand. This suggests that during the initial curing phase of MOC-based samples, a reaction occurs that incorporates the released zinc into the cement matrix, resulting in a more complex hybrid cement. Concentrations of Cd, Se, and Zn in the investigated leachates were assessed in accordance with the thresholds stipulated by the Czech Ordinance on details of waste management No. 273/2021, Annex 5 and Annex 10 [54], regarding wastes for use as backfilling or safe landfill disposal without environmental risk. The limits for heavy elements specified in Ordinance No. 273/2021 are expressed in units of ppm, such as 0.7 ppm for Cd and Se, and 70 ppm for Zn. The measured values presented in Table 11, expressed in units of $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, are equivalent to units of ppb. None of the analysed heavy metals (HMs) demonstrated concentrations exceeding the prescribed limits. Consequently, this evidence substantiates the efficient immobilisation of contaminating HMs within the formulated composites.

4. Conclusion

The presented work explored the potential of recycled waste glass cullet from beads production to partially or fully substitute silica sand in MOC (magnesium oxychloride cement) composite materials. The mechanical strength and Young's modulus of samples incorporating waste glass cullet exhibited no significant deviation from those of the reference materials. Replacing 25 % of the sand with recycled glass slightly improved mechanical properties, linked to open porosity data. A 50 % sand substitution with glass cullet is optimal, indicating strong mechanical parameters for broad construction industry use. For MOC-C-25 % and MOC-C-50 %, the softening coefficient showed little change from the reference. Glass recycle reduced water absorption but eventually led to reduced strength. However, residual strength stayed high enough for structural use. MOC-C-100 % showed improved softening coefficient over the reference. In summary, the research carried out shows that recycled waste glass from glass bead manufacturing is an effective alternative to natural silica sand as a filler. It enhances MOC composites with strong mechanical resistance, less water penetration, and good durability. Colour variations support its use in construction, and it helps reduce environmental risks from heavy metal contaminants like Zn, Se, and Cd in glass recycle.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Klouzková Alexandra: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Data curation. **Jankovský Ondřej:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Data curation. **Lauermannová Anna-Marie:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Záleská Martina:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Kolářová Mária:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Pavlík Zbyšek:** Writing –

review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Pivák Adam:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Pavlíková Milena:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at doi:10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2025.141649.

Data availability

The raw data is stored under the following DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14834341.

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